

Mapping Research Topics of the Determinants and Influence of Basic Earning Power (BEP) on Sharia and Conventional Financial Institutions: VOSviewer Bibliometric Study and Literature Review

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Abstract

This study aims to determine the map of research developments regarding determinant variables and the influence of Basic Earning Power/BEP on Islamic and Conventional Financial Institutions using a mix-method approach, namely quantitative methods in bibliometric studies and qualitative methods in literature review studies. The research object is Basic Earning Power/BEP. The source of data collection comes from searches of national journals indexed by Google Scholar and Sinta through the Perish/Harzing application. Data analysis techniques include: (1) mapping RIS data files on Mendeley Desktop based on the order of year, author, and publisher; (2) mapping the results of visualization of bibliometric networks and trends in scientific publications using the VOSviewer algorithm software (Visualization of Similarities); and (3) mapping research topics. The results showed that the number of publications has increased significantly every year. And based on the mapping results using the VOSviewer application and literature review, there are 2 main themes around the determinant variables and the influence of Basic Earning Power/BEP. The implication and contribution of this research is to map topics that are often researched by researchers, so that they can find out research gaps, and can become a reference for subsequent researchers.

Keywords: Basic Earning Power/BEP, Bibliometrics, VOSviewer, Literature Review, Islamic and Conventional Financial Institutions

Introduction

the Basic Earning Power (BEP) ratio in financial institutions has undergone several changes over time. Initially, the BEP ratio was used as a tool to compare performance between financial institutions. However, over time, the use of this ratio has developed into a more complex tool that can assist financial institution management in identifying operational weaknesses and potential performance improvements. Basically, the BEP ratio provides an overview of how effectively a financial institution's assets are used to generate profits. The higher the BEP ratio, the more effective the financial institution is in using its assets to generate profits. Conversely, the lower the BEP ratio, the less effective the financial institution is in using its assets to generate profits.

In an increasingly complex financial institution environment, the use of BEP ratios has been enhanced with additional metrics such as Return on Equity (ROE), Return on Assets (ROA), Net Interest Margin (NIM), and Cost-to-Income Ratio (CIR). ROE measures the effectiveness of using shareholder capital in generating net profits, while ROA measures the ability of a financial institution to generate profits from the assets it owns. NIM measures the difference between interest income generated by the bank and interest costs paid by the bank, while CIR measures the efficiency of bank costs in generating income. In combination with these ratios, the BEP ratio can provide more holistic information about a bank's financial health and operational performance. Developments in

technology and data analysis have enabled financial institutions to use more sophisticated predictive models to improve the use of BEP ratios. This model uses historical data to estimate future performance and helps bank management identify long-term trends and potential operational improvements. Additionally, developments in technology and data analysis have enabled financial institutions to use more sophisticated predictive models to improve the use of BEP ratios. In this case, historical data is used to estimate future performance and enable bank management to identify long-term trends and potential operational improvements. Overall, the use of BEP ratios in financial institutions has evolved over time and become a more complex and informative tool. The use of this ratio will continue to grow along with developments in the financial institution industry and advances in technology and data analysis. The BEP ratio and other financial ratios are very important for bank management to monitor financial and operational performance and improve bank performance to achieve strategic goals.

Research on BEP in financial institutions continues to grow along with the development of the financial institution industry itself. Several recent studies have explored the use of BEP in different contexts, such as in developing countries and in the context of financial institution regulation. A study shows that the use of BEP in the financial institutions industry in China can help banks improve efficiency and minimize financial risks. The research found that banks that have a higher BEP tend to be more stable and more susceptible to lower financial risks. Other research shows that the use of BEP in the financial institutions industry can help identify banks that are likely to experience financial difficulties in the future. They found that banks with lower BEP tend to experience financial difficulties in the long term. Overall, research on BEP in financial institutions continues to grow and provides valuable insights for banks and financial decision makers. In a financial institution industry that is constantly changing and developing, the use of financial ratios such as BEP can help banks to measure their performance effectively and take appropriate actions to maximize efficiency and reduce financial risks. Based on the problems above, mapping of financing risk management topics is needed to identify, measure and control risks that will occur. This can fulfill the need for human resources tasked with risk management to have knowledge, skills and work attitudes according to the bank's needs.

The aim of this research is to map research topics around Basic Earning Power (BEP) in Sharia and Conventional Financial Institutions using: (1) the VOSviewer bibliometric method to analyze and study maps of literature development in publications in a scientific field by creating a metadata network map; and (2) literature review studies to analyze, identify and review articles from the accredited national journal Sinta. The difference between this research and previous research is that this research explains all research topics regarding Basic Earning Power (BEP) in Sharia and Conventional Financial Institutions. This can be a reference for other researchers who wish to research Basic Earning Power (BEP). The implication and contribution of this research is to map topics that are often researched by researchers, so that they can identify research gaps, and can become a reference for subsequent researchers.

Literature Review

Basic Earning Power (BEP) is a financial ratio used to measure the financial performance of a financial institution. This ratio calculates a financial institution's ability to generate income from its assets without considering the

effects of capital structure or cost of debt. In general, BEP calculates a bank's earnings before interest and taxes (EBIT) divided by the financial institution's total assets. This ratio shows how much income the bank generates from each unit of assets it owns. The higher the BEP ratio, the better the bank's financial performance in utilizing its assets to generate income.

Bibliometric studies constitute analytical methods used to measure and analyze quantitatively from scientific publications. This method involves collecting and analyzing bibliographic data from sources such as journals, books, and conferences, with the aim of identifying trends, patterns, and distinct research topics. Bibliometric studies involve the use of statistical methods and data analysis to gain insight into academic performance, researcher productivity, or journal rankings in a scientific field. Bibliometric studies can be conducted using a variety of methods, including citation analysis, co-citation analysis, and co-authorship analysis. Citation analysis studies the frequency and patterns of citations in scientific papers, while co-citation analysis studies the same citation patterns between pairs of publications. Co-authorship analysis studies collaboration patterns between authors in a research field. Using this method, researchers can identify patterns of connection between authors, research topics, or publications, and provide insight into the influence and significance of a research field. Bibliometric studies are used in various fields of science, including social sciences, natural sciences, medicine, and humanities. This method can help researchers map research developments in a field, identify important research topics, and measure the impact and significance of research.

VOSviewer is Bibliometric data analysis method used to analyze the relationship between keywords, authors and publications in a network. VOSviewer can be used to visualize and analyze various types of bibliometric data, including citations, co-citations, and co-authorship. This method can help in identifying trends, patterns, and research topics that are trending or important in a field, as well as in mapping and classifying different research topics. VOSviewer allows users to visualize data in various types of graphs, including network maps, bar graphs, and line graphs. This method can also be used to identify research groups or authors who frequently collaborate, as well as to identify popular or under-researched research topics within a field. In academic research, VOSviewer can be used to assist researchers in developing a better understanding of the research area they are researching, as well as to strengthen the credibility and relevance of that research.

Studies literature review is a systematic process for collecting, evaluating, and analyzing information contained in scientific publications, books, and other sources relevant to a particular topic. The purpose of a literature review study is to gain a comprehensive understanding of a particular topic, evaluate research that has been conducted previously, identify gaps in existing research, and gain new insight into the topic being studied. Literature review studies can be carried out in various fields, including social sciences, natural sciences, medicine, and humanities.

Methodology

This research uses research methods with a mix-method approach, namely quantitative methods in bibliometric studies and qualitative methods in literature review studies. The research object is Basic Earning Power/BEP. The type of data used is secondary data. The scope of the data used is research

journal articles on Basic Earning Power/BEP in Sharia and Conventional financial institutions.

The source of data collection comes from search for national and international journals indexed by Google Scholar And Sinta via the Perish/Harzing application. Data analysis tools use Microsoft Excel software, Mendeley Desktop, and VOSviewer. Data collection techniques include: (1) opening Perish/Harzing software, then search for journals based on the title words category with the keyword " Basic Earning Power/BEP" in the entire year period (1995 -2022); (2) collect journal title data in Microsoft Excel, and identify duplicate journal titles; (3) download files in RIS (Research Information Systems) and PDF (Portable Document Format) formats from all journals for which data has been collected; and (4) inserting the RIS data file into Mendeley Desktop software.

Data analysis techniques include: (1) mapping RIS data files on Mendeley Desktop based on year, author and publisher; (2) mapping the results of bibliometric network visualization and scientific publication trends using the VOSviewer (Visualization of Similarities) algorithm software based on the number of clusters and items; and (3) mapping topics research based on literature review studies.

Results and Discussion

Mapping the Distribution of Scientific Publications Regarding Basic Earning Power/BEP in Sharia and Conventional Financial Institutions

There are 50 national journals accredited by Sinta based on the results of data collection from the Perish/Harzing application during the period 1995 to 2022.

Journal publication data regarding Legal Risk by year

Year	Number of Publications	Year	Number of Publications	Year	Number of Publications
1995	1	2010	3	2018	4
1996	1	2012	1	2019	2
1997	2	2014	3	2020	5
1999	3	2015	3	2021	2
2006	1	2016	6	2022	6
2009	1	2017	5		

Source: Processed data, Microsoft Excel 2016.

Bibliometric Mapping of Research Regarding Basic Earning Power/BEP in Sharia and Conventional Financial Institutions

Search results for articles on software Perish/Harzing are exported in RIS (Research Information Systems) format, then input and analyzed using VOSviewer software. The results are as follows:

variable, indicator, real influence, rest, secondary source, stock price, capital structure, t test, variables.

- Cluster 5, purple, consists of 14 topic items, namely : economic influence analysis, return, roe, equity, eva, investors, net profit margin, economic value, quick ratio, stock return, total assets, test.
- Cluster 6, light blue, consists of 10 topic items, namely : dividend payout ratio, dpr, Indonesian stock exchange, investment, investment opportunity, ios, influence of returns, return, roi sample.
- Cluster 7, red, consists of 6 topic items, namely : time interest, currency, the influence of world oil prices, power, on stock prices, utility.
- Cluster 8, brown, consists of 3 topic items, namely : assets, asset turn, receivable turn.

Mapping Literature Review regarding the Influence of Basic Earning Power/BEP on Sharia and Conventional financial institutions

literature review study in previous research journals, researchers found 6 influences of Basic Earning Power/BEP on Sharia and Conventional financial institutions, namely:

First, Dividend Payout Ratio/DPR. The influence of BEP on DPR in financial institutions is as follows: (1) Increasing the Ability to Distribute Dividends: The higher the BEP ratio, the greater the bank's ability to generate profits from the assets it owns. This can increase the amount of profit available to be distributed in the form of dividends, thereby potentially increasing the DPR. (2) Reducing Shareholder Risk: A high BEP indicates that the bank is able to generate sufficient profits to meet financial obligations and provide profits to shareholders. This can reduce shareholder risk and increase their trust in the bank, thereby potentially increasing DPR. (3) Influence Bank Dividend Policy: BEP can influence bank decisions in determining dividend policy. If the BEP is high, the bank may be more inclined to pay larger dividends to shareholders. However, if the BEP is low, the bank may prefer to retain profits and use them to expand the business or pay down debt.

Second, Earning Per Share/EPS. The influence of BEP on EPS in financial institutions is as follows: (1) Shows Operational Efficiency: The higher the BEP ratio, the more efficient the bank is in generating profits from the assets it owns. This can lead to an increase in EPS because bank profits become greater. (2) Lower Bank Risk: A low BEP can indicate higher risk to the bank. This can reduce EPS because bank profits will be smaller. (3) Influences Bank Capital Structure: The BEP ratio can influence a bank's decision in choosing sources of funds, such as debt or shares, which in turn can affect EPS.

Third, stock price. BEP can influence share prices in financial institutions in several ways: (1) Shows Operational Efficiency: The higher the BEP ratio, the more efficient the bank is in generating profits from the assets it owns. This can increase investors' confidence that the bank will be able to generate higher profits in the future, which can lead to an increase in share prices. (2) Indicates Bank Risk: A low BEP may indicate higher risk as the bank may have difficulty generating sufficient profits to offset its operational costs. This can reduce investor confidence in banks and reduce share prices. (3) Affects Credit Ratings: The BEP ratio can also affect a bank's credit rating, which can impact share prices. Banks with high BEP ratios can be considered more stable and can have better credit ratings, which can increase share prices.

Fourth, Market Value Added/MVA. The influence of BEP on MVA in financial institutions is as follows: (1) Increasing Added Value: The higher the BEP ratio, the more efficient the bank is in generating profits from its assets. This can increase the bank's added value, thereby having a positive impact on MVA. (2) Indicates Growth Potential: A high BEP can indicate a bank's greater growth potential in the future, as the bank has a better ability to generate profits from its assets. This can increase the bank's added value and have a positive impact on MVA. (3) Strengthening Bank Performance: A high BEP ratio can indicate that the bank has strong and stable performance, which can increase investor confidence and strengthen the bank's market value. This can have a positive impact on MVA.

Fifth, Price to Book Value/PBV. The influence of BEP on PBV in financial institutions is as follows: (1) Increasing Bank Market Value: The higher the BEP ratio, the more efficient the bank is in generating profits from its assets. This can increase investor confidence and strengthen the bank's market value, thereby having a positive impact on PBV. (2) Strengthening Bank Performance: A high BEP can indicate that the bank has strong and stable performance, which can increase investor confidence and strengthen the bank's market value. This can have a positive impact on PBV. (3) Increase the Bank's Book Value: The higher the BEP ratio, the greater the profit generated by the bank from its assets. This can increase the bank's book value, which can have a positive impact on PBV.

Sixth, stock returns. The influence of BEP on stock returns in financial institutions is as follows: (1) Increasing investor confidence: The higher the BEP ratio, the more efficient the bank is in generating profits from its assets. This can increase investor confidence and strengthen the bank's market value, which in turn can increase stock returns. (2) Strengthening Bank Performance: A high BEP can indicate that the bank has strong and stable performance, which can increase investor confidence and strengthen the bank's market value. This can have a positive impact on stock returns. (3) Increasing Profit Potential: The higher the BEP ratio, the greater the potential profit that the bank can generate from its assets. This can increase potential profits for shareholders and have a positive impact on stock returns.

Mapping Literature Review regarding the Determinant Variables of Basic Earning Power/BEP in Sharia and Conventional financial institutions

literature review study in previous research journals, researchers found 15 determinant variables of Basic Earning Power/BEP in Sharia and Conventional financial institutions, namely:

First, Current Ratio. The influence of the Current Ratio on BEP in financial institutions is as follows: (1) Affects the Bank's Ability to Generate Profits: A high Current Ratio indicates that the bank has sufficient liquidity to pay its short-term obligations, but it can also indicate that the bank may have insufficient assets. productive. This can affect the bank's ability to generate profits from the assets it owns, which can have an impact on the BEP ratio. (2) Affecting the Efficiency of Asset Use: A low Current Ratio can indicate that the bank is having difficulty paying its short-term obligations, which can have an impact on the efficiency of using the bank's assets. This can affect the BEP ratio, as the bank may have to pay higher interest on its short-term debt. (3) Relationship Between Liquidity and Profitability: The relationship between liquidity and profitability is not always in the same direction in financial institutions. Even though a high Current Ratio indicates that the bank has good

liquidity, this does not always mean that the bank can generate greater profits. Therefore, it is necessary to carry out further analysis to determine a more specific influence of the Current Ratio on BEP in financial institutions.

Second, Debt to Equity Ratio/DER. The influence of DER on BEP in financial institutions can be explained as follows: (1) Influences Interest Expenses: A high DER indicates that the bank has a large interest burden, so it can affect the bank's ability to generate profits from the assets it owns. Because BEP does not take into account interest expenses, a high DER can reduce the BEP ratio. (2) Affects Bank Risk: A high DER can indicate that a bank is riskier and has a higher probability of experiencing financial difficulties. This can affect the bank's ability to generate profits from the assets it owns, which can have an impact on the BEP ratio. (3) Influences Capital Structure: A high DER indicates that the bank uses more debt in its capital structure. This can affect bank operational financing, which in turn can affect the bank's ability to generate profits from the assets it owns. (4) Leverage Potential: On the other hand, a low DER can indicate that the bank has greater leverage potential, which can increase the bank's ability to generate profits from the assets it owns.

Third, Fixed Assets Turn Over/FATO. The influence of FATO on BEP in financial institutions can be explained as follows: (1) Influences Income Generating Ability: A high FATO indicates that the bank is effective in utilizing fixed assets to generate income. This can increase the bank's ability to generate profits from the assets it owns, which can have an impact on the BEP ratio. (2) Affects Operational Efficiency: A low FATO can indicate that the bank is less effective in utilizing fixed assets and generating income. This can affect the bank's operational efficiency, which in turn can affect the bank's ability to generate profits from the assets it owns. (3) Affects Investment Levels: A low FATO may indicate that the bank requires greater investment in fixed assets to increase earnings. This can affect the bank's ability to generate profits from the assets it owns and can have an impact on the BEP ratio. (4) Affects Bank Risk: A high FATO can indicate that the bank has lower risk and is more stable in generating income. This can affect the bank's ability to generate profits from the assets it owns and can have an impact on the BEP ratio.

Fourth, Good Corporate Governance/GCG. The influence of GCG on BEP in financial institutions can be explained as follows: (1) Transparency and Accountability: Good GCG can increase bank transparency and accountability, thereby improving risk management and financial management. This can increase the bank's ability to generate greater profits from the assets owned and have an impact on the BEP ratio. (2) Risk Management: Good GCG can improve bank risk management, including financial, operational and reputation risks. This can strengthen the bank's sustainability in the long term and can increase the bank's ability to generate profits from the assets owned and have an impact on the BEP ratio. (3) Fairness: Good GCG can increase fairness in decision making and allocation of bank resources. This can increase the efficiency and effectiveness of the bank, and can have an impact on the bank's ability to generate profits from the assets owned and impact the BEP ratio. (4) Bank Social Responsibility: Good GCG can increase the bank's social responsibility and its positive impact on the environment, society and employees. This can improve the bank's reputation and investor confidence, which in turn can increase share value and impact the BEP ratio.

Fifth, Long Term Debt to Equity Ratio (LTD/E). The influence of LTD/E on BEP in financial institutions can be explained as follows: (1) Risk Level: If LTD/E is higher, it will increase the bank's financial risk. This is because the

higher the amount of debt you have, the higher the interest rate the bank must pay, and the higher the risk of default or default. This risk will affect the bank's ability to generate greater profits from the assets owned, and have an impact on the BEP ratio. (2) Cost of Capital: If the LTD/E is higher, the bank's cost of capital will also be higher. This is because the more debt you have, the greater the interest the bank must pay. High capital costs will affect the bank's ability to generate greater profits from the assets owned, and have an impact on the BEP ratio. (3) Investment Decision: If LTD/E is higher, it will be more difficult for banks to obtain funding for long-term investments. This can affect the bank's ability to generate profits from its assets and impact the BEP ratio.

Sixth, working capital turnover. The influence of WCT on BEP in financial institutions can be explained as follows: (1) Operational Efficiency: The higher the WCT, the more efficient the bank is in using working capital to generate income. This can increase BEP because banks can generate greater income from the assets they own. (2) Credit Risk: The higher the WCT, the less credit the bank provides to customers. This can reduce credit risk and improve the quality of bank assets. Low credit risk can also increase investor confidence and increase the value of bank shares. (3) Cost of Capital: The higher the WCT, the lower the capital cost that the bank must bear. This is because the more efficient the bank is in using working capital to generate income, the less costs the bank has to incur to finance its operations.

Seventh, total asset turnover. The influence of TAT on BEP in financial institutions can be explained as follows: (1) Operational Efficiency: The higher the TAT, the more efficient the bank is in using total assets to generate income. This can increase BEP because banks can generate greater income from the total assets owned. (2) Credit Risk: The higher the TAT, the more credit the bank provides to customers. This can increase credit risk and reduce the quality of bank assets. High credit risk can also reduce investor confidence and reduce the value of bank shares. (3) Cost of Capital: The higher the TAT, the higher the cost of capital that the bank must bear. This is because the more efficient the bank is in using total assets to generate income, the more costs the bank must incur to finance its operations.

Eighth, economic growth. The influence of economic growth on BEP in financial institutions can be explained as follows: (1) Income Growth: High economic growth can increase customer income and the volume of financial transactions. This can increase the financial institution's income, which in turn can increase the financial institution's BEP. (2) Increase in Interest Rates: High economic growth can lead to an increase in interest rates. This can increase the financial institution's profit margin and in turn increase the financial institution's BEP. (3) Credit Risk: High economic growth can trigger an increase in demand for credit. However, credit risk can also increase because less qualified customers can obtain credit more easily. This can reduce the BEP of financial institutions because higher credit risk can increase operational costs. (4) Competition: High economic growth can attract more competitors into the financial institutions industry. Tighter competition can suppress financial institutions' profit margins and reduce financial institutions' BEP.

Ninth, Return On Assets/ROA. The influence of ROA on BEP in financial institutions can be seen as follows: (1) High ROA can increase the BEP of financial institutions. The higher the ROA of a financial institution, the greater the financial institution's ability to generate profits from its total assets. Thus, the greater the possibility of a financial institution to generate profits before taking into account the financial burden and taxes, which constitute the BEP.

(2) Low BEP can affect the ROA of a financial institution. If a financial institution's BEP is low, it means that the financial institution requires greater financial costs and taxes to generate profits. This can reduce the ROA of a financial institution because ROA measures the profits generated by a financial institution from its total assets.

In order to increase ROA and BEP, financial institutions can take several actions, including: (1) Increasing operational efficiency and reducing costs. Financial institutions can make efficiencies in their operations by improving systems and business processes that are more effective and efficient. In this way, operational costs can be reduced and the BEP of financial institutions can increase. (2) Expanding customer and product bases. Financial institutions can increase ROA and BEP by expanding their customer base and offering new, more profitable products and services. The larger the customer base and the more products offered, the greater the opportunity to increase profits and ROA of a financial institution. (3) Manage risks better. Financial institutions can increase ROA and BEP by better managing risk. In carrying out its business activities, financial institutions must pay attention to the risks they face and take the necessary precautions to minimize these risks. In this way, financial institutions can improve their performance and increase ROA and BEP.

Tenth, Receivable Turn Over. The influence of Receivable Turnover on BEP in financial institutions can be explained as follows: (1) High RT can increase the BEP of financial institutions. The higher the RT of a financial institution, the faster the financial institution can collect receivables from customers. This can increase the financial institution's cash flow and allow the financial institution to generate more profits from operations. Thus, high RT can increase the BEP of financial institutions. (2) Low BEP can affect the RT of financial institutions. If a financial institution's BEP is low, it means that the financial institution requires greater financial costs and taxes to generate profits. This can affect a financial institution's ability to collect receivables from customers quickly. Thus, low BEP can affect the RT of financial institutions.

In order to improve RT and BEP, financial institutions can take several actions, including: (1) Improving the receivables collection process. Financial institutions can improve the receivables collection process to speed up RT. For example, by improving billing systems, financial institutions can speed up the process of collecting receivables from customers. (2) Increase operational efficiency. By improving operational efficiency, financial institutions can speed up the receivables collection process and improve their BEP. For example, by increasing business process automation, financial institutions can reduce operational costs and increase their operating profits. (3) Reduce credit risk. Financial institutions can reduce credit risk by tightening credit requirements and improving credit monitoring. In this way, financial institutions can minimize credit risk and increase their RT and BEP. (4) Offer more profitable products and services. By offering more profitable products and services, financial institutions can increase their revenues and operating profits. For example, by offering digital products and services, financial institutions can increase the number of customers and speed up the process of collecting receivables from customers.

Eleventh, Time Interest Earned Ratio. The influence of the Time Interest Earned Ratio on Basic Earning Power in financial institutions can be explained as follows: (1) High TIER can increase the BEP of financial institutions. The higher the TIER of a financial institution, the easier it is for the financial institution to pay interest on its debt. This can increase investor confidence and

help financial institutions to obtain cheaper financing. Thus, a high TIER can increase the BEP of a financial institution. (2) Low BEP can affect the TIER of financial institutions. If a financial institution's BEP is low, it means that the financial institution requires greater financial costs and taxes to generate profits. This can affect a financial institution's ability to pay interest on its debt. Thus, a low BEP can affect the TIER of a financial institution.

In order to increase TIER and BEP, financial institutions can take several actions, including: (1) Optimizing capital structure. Financial institutions can optimize their capital structure by reducing debt levels or increasing equity levels. In this way, financial institutions can reduce interest costs and increase their TIER and BEP. (2) Manage risks well. Financial institutions can manage risk well to minimize the risk of debt repayment failure. For example, financial institutions can conduct better credit risk analysis or tighten credit requirements. In this way, financial institutions can increase their ability to pay interest on their debt and increase their TIER and BEP. (3) Increase operational income. By increasing operating income, financial institutions can increase their operating profits and increase their ability to pay interest on their debt. For example, by offering more profitable products and services, financial institutions can increase their revenues and operating profits. (4) Optimizing operational expenses. By optimizing operational expenses, financial institutions can reduce financial burdens and increase their TIER and BEP. For example, by reducing operational costs or optimizing other expenses, a financial institution can increase its operating profit and ability to pay interest on its debt.

Twelfth, Return On Equity/ROE. The influence of Return on Equity (ROE) on Basic Earning Power/BEP in financial institutions can be explained as follows: (1) High ROE can increase the BEP of financial institutions. The higher the ROE of a financial institution, the more effectively the bank uses its equity to generate profits. With a high ROE, a bank can increase its BEP by allocating funds to projects that generate higher profits. (2) Low BEP can affect the ROE of financial institutions. If a financial institution's BEP is low, it means that the bank requires greater financial costs and taxes to generate profits. This can affect the ROE of financial institutions, because the profits generated are not commensurate with the capital invested.

In order to increase ROE and BEP, financial institutions can take several actions, including: (1) Optimizing the use of capital. Financial institutions can optimize the use of their capital by allocating funds to projects that generate higher profits. In this way, financial institutions can increase their ROE and BEP. (2) Increase operational efficiency. Financial institutions can increase their operational efficiency by reducing operational costs and increasing productivity. In this way, financial institutions can increase their operating profits and their ROE and BEP. (3) Increase return on assets. Financial institutions can increase their return on assets by optimizing the use of their assets and reducing unproductive assets. In this way, financial institutions can increase their ROE and BEP. (4) Manage risks well. Financial institutions can manage risk well to minimize the risk of debt payment failure and other losses. In this way, a financial institution can increase investor confidence and generate higher profits, which in turn can increase its ROE and BEP.

Thirteenth, Net Interest Margin/NIM. The influence of Net Interest Margin (NIM) on Basic Earning Power/BEP in financial institutions can be explained as follows: (1) A high NIM can increase the BEP of financial institutions. The higher the NIM of a financial institution, the greater the interest income received by the

bank and the smaller the interest costs the bank must pay. This can increase the BEP of financial institutions because banks can generate more profits from operations. (2) Low BEP can affect the NIM of financial institutions. If a financial institution's BEP is low, it means that the bank requires greater financial costs to generate profits. This can affect the NIM of financial institutions, because banks have to pay more interest for their funding.

In order to increase NIM and BEP, financial institutions can take several actions, including: (1) Maintaining asset quality. Financial institutions can maintain the quality of their assets by minimizing credit risk and balancing their loan portfolios. In this way, a financial institution can minimize credit risk costs and increase its NIM and BEP. (2) Optimizing the fund structure. Financial institutions can optimize their fund structure by looking for cheap and stable funding sources, such as savings deposits and time deposits. In this way, financial institutions can minimize funding costs and increase their NIM and BEP. (3) Maintain operational efficiency. Financial institutions can maintain operational efficiency by reducing operational costs and increasing productivity. In this way, financial institutions can increase their operating profits and their NIM and BEP. (4) Adjust interest rates. Financial institutions can adjust the interest rates given to customers according to market conditions. In this way, financial institutions can maximize interest income and increase their NIM and BEP.

Fourteenth, Loan to Deposit Ratio/LDR. The influence of Loan to Deposit Ratio (LDR) on Basic Earning Power/BEP in financial institutions can be explained as follows: (1) High LDR can increase the BEP of financial institutions. The higher the LDR of a financial institution, the greater the loan amount provided by the bank. Thus, banks can generate more interest income which can increase the BEP of financial institutions. (2) Low LDR can reduce the BEP of financial institutions. If a financial institution's LDR is low, it means that the bank has more sources of funds but they are not used effectively to provide loans that generate interest income. This can reduce the BEP of financial institutions because banks cannot utilize their savings optimally.

In order to increase LDR and BEP, financial institutions can take several actions, including: (1) Developing appropriate loan products. Financial institutions can develop loan products that suit customer needs to increase loan demand. In this way, banks can increase their LDR and BEP. (2) Improving credit quality. Financial institutions can improve their credit quality by conducting careful credit analysis and managing credit risk well. In this way, banks can increase the number of approved loans and minimize credit risks. This can increase the LDR and BEP. (3) Improve product and service marketing. Financial institutions can improve the marketing of their products and services to attract new customers. In this way, banks can increase the amount of deposits they receive and expand their customer base. This can increase the LDR and BEP. (4) Manage liquidity well. Financial institutions can manage their liquidity well to ensure that the deposit funds received can be used effectively to provide loans that generate interest income. In this way, banks can increase their LDR and BEP.

Fifteenth, Non Performing Loans/NPL. The influence of Non-Performing Loans (NPL) on BEP in financial institutions can be explained as follows: (1) High NPLs can reduce the BEP of financial institutions. If a bank has a high level of NPL, it means that the bank faces higher credit risk and must take action to deal with this problem, such as preparing reserves for impairment losses (CKPNV) or reducing credit distribution. This action can reduce interest income

and net profit which reduces the BEP of financial institutions. (2) Low NPL can increase the BEP of financial institutions. If a bank has a low NPL level, it means the bank can minimize its credit risk and can increase the amount of loans approved. Thus, banks can increase their interest income and net profit which increases the BEP of financial institutions.

In order to manage credit risk and increase BEP, financial institutions can take several actions, including: (1) Improving credit quality. Financial institutions can improve their credit quality by conducting careful credit analysis, tightening lending requirements and properly monitoring approved credit. In this way, the bank can minimize its credit risk and increase its BEP. (2) Improving credit portfolio management. Financial institutions can improve their credit portfolio management by regularly monitoring existing credit risks and eliminating NPLs in a timely manner. In this way, banks can improve the quality of their credit portfolio and increase their BEP. (3) Maintain liquidity well. Financial institutions can maintain their liquidity well to ensure that the deposit funds received can be used effectively to provide loans that generate interest income. In this way, banks can minimize credit risks and increase their BEP. (4) Improve risk control. Financial institutions can improve risk control by having a good risk management system and carrying out continuous risk assessments. In this way, banks can identify credit risks that may arise and take appropriate action to overcome them so as to increase their BEP.

Conclusions and Recommendations

Based on the results of the discussion above, it can be concluded as follows:

- The number of research publications regarding Basic Earning Power/BEP in Sharia and Conventional financial institutions during the period 1995 to 2022 shows a significant increase from year to year. The total number of publications is 50 research articles.
- In the mapping visualization using the VOS viewer, research developments regarding Basic Earning Power/BEP in Sharia and Conventional financial institutions are divided into 8 clusters.
- Based on the literature review, there are seven main research themes, namely: determinant variables and the influence of Basic Earning Power/BEP on Sharia and Conventional financial institutions.

is recommended that further research use a larger data sample, so that it can explain a broader research mapping, considering the limitations of the data sample in this study and can add a longer research data time span so that the following research results can be obtained:

- It is hoped that the mapping results will show a higher and broader level of generalization.
- The results of the e- review literature study can be explained in a more complex way.

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